

Dear Don't Look Up team,

Thank you for giving us the opportunity to submit a revised draft of our Data Management Plan titled "[La Chouffe - Revised DMP](#)" to Zenodo. We appreciate the time and effort that you and the reviewers have dedicated to providing your valuable feedback on "[La Chouffe DMP New](#)". We are grateful to the reviewers for their insightful comments our plan. We have been able to incorporate changes to reflect most of the suggestions provided by the reviewers. We have highlighted the changes within our DMP.

Here is a point-by-point response to the reviewers' comments and concerns.

Comments from "[Review of: La Chouffe DMP New](#)" by Chiara Manca

Comment 1: I suggest to add the resulting dataset that the research originated as new data. It is unclear if the datasets that are currently specified in the DMP and their answers regard the results of the research or the actual Crossref and DOAJ data.

Response: Thank you for pointing this out. We agree with this comment. Therefore, we have changed our DMP that now is made up of two datasets and one software. "DOAJ and Crossref Aggregated Data" (p. 3 to 7) will store the results of the research, instead "DOAJ data" (p. 13 to 18) is the actual DOAJ article dump simplified to DOI, ISSN and publication year informations in order to make it a bit lighter.

Comment 2: All the questions regarding how it will be collected and described seem correct but I suggest that this information could be inserted inside the description of a general dataset that represents the results of the research.

Response: Agree. We have, accordingly, modified our DMP adding aggregation and structural datasets information in their relative description (p. 3 and 13) to emphasise this point.

Comment 3: In the questions about Reused Data it will be then specified that this data came from the combination and reuse of Crossref and DOAJ data, providing the information about its provenance and accessibility.

Response: We agree with this and have incorporated your suggestion in Reuse Data section.

Comment 4: Topics of backup and security are touched: it is said that the data will be kept secure and available on Github but procedures about backup and recovery are not specified, nor the frequency of them. Also the URL of the repository could be provided in the future.

Response: Agree. We add in the DMP description URL to Github repository. In addition, we have added accurate descriptions to each component of the DMP on where the data will be stored on insecure, unmanaged storage for limited time.

Comment 5: The plan specifies that the data will be made openly accessible on Github. Of course in the future they should be matching the data to a license that will assure this statement. Also, if they plan to reuse data they will have to make sure to eventually cite authorship or follow any guideline that the license of the data requires, as they specified in the La Software description. There is no specification about the licenses that they will be using for their datasets. They mention that they want to make all of their data openly available in Github, so, for the software, I suggest some kind of license that will ensure the specification of authorship and, for the actual data, the most open license that they find.

Response: You have raised an important point here. However, we believe that an accurate research and discussion before closing a licence would be more appropriate because, as you point it out, it's a sensible issue. At the moment in our new version we specify for Software that "We are currently discussing which license to choose. The ones we will probably use are the ISC license of the MIT one." (P.11). Instead, both datasets are licensed by CC0 1.0. Do you have any suggestions?

Comments from "[Review of: La Chouffe DMP New](#)" by Umut Kucuk

Comment 1: *brief predictions about the data likely to emerge at the end of the project could be included.*

Response: Agree. We have, accordingly, modified the description of our datasets to emphasize this point. We briefly explain method, purposes, description and manipulation made on data.

Comment 2: *Reusability is an extremely important aspect for a research in this domain. A more descriptive and comprehensive narrative on the reuse of data, both used in the content of the project and that will emerge as a result of the project, could make a very positive contribution to the project.*

Response: Thank you for pointing this out. We agree with this comment. Therefore, we have expand the Reusability sections in our DMP adding more information about accessing methods and possible users interested in our domain.

Comment 3: *It is also stated that the metadata will be harvestable. In this section, more detailed information can be given in the light of the methodological approach followed, as the study progresses.*

Response: Thank you for this suggestion. We add in section "MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA" more explanation regarding methodological approach followed to choose metadata (Dublincore) and to store metadata (RDF/Turtle)

Comment 4: *On the other hand carrying out a detailed approach to data security and backup is important for the sustainability of the project. Additional information on this topic would improve the project.*

Response: Agree. We have, accordingly, revised DMP to emphasize this point. We add in the DMP description URL to Github repository. In addition, we have added accurate descriptions to each component of the DMP on where the data will be stored on insecure, unmanaged storage for limited time.

Additional clarifications

In addition to the above comments, all spelling and grammatical errors pointed out by the reviewers have been corrected.

We look forward to hearing from you in due time regarding our submission and to respond to any further questions and comments you may have.

Sincerely,

La Chouffe Team

26/04/2022